

Directed forgetting of memories in cocaine users

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Abstract

Memory retrieval requires an effective recruitment of inhibitory control to successfully reject unnecessary memories. The use of cocaine is associated with poor cognitive control processes, but little is known about the impact of chronic and recreational use of cocaine on inhibitory control during intentional forgetting. We studied whether chronic and recreational users of cocaine show impairments on the mechanism responsible for intentional forgetting of memories. Two experiments were carried out on chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation (Experiment 1) and recreational cocaine polydrug users (Experiment 2) performing a directed forgetting (DF) task, an index of memory suppression. Participants were matched for sex, age, and intelligence (Raven's standard progressive matrices) with cocaine-free controls and compared on their performance on a DF procedure. Chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation and recreational cocaine polydrug users, as compared to controls, were not able to intentionally suppress the required information and they did not show a reliable DF effect. The consumption of cocaine appears to alter the control processes implicated in intentional suppression of non-relevant memories in episodic memory. The use of cocaine, even for recreational purposes, seems to be associated with poor performance in effectively triggering this control mechanism. The inability to suppress interference in declarative memory may have repercussion for daily activities.

Keywords: cocaine, memory suppression, inhibition

Public Significance Statement

This study suggests that the abuse of cocaine, whether chronic or recreational, led to impairments in the cognitive mechanism that allows the suppression of irrelevant memories. It may be translated into a variety of memory distortions in terms of updating of information,

which may affect recall in everyday situations, causing difficulties in the acquisition of new information or affecting the ability to forget negative autobiographical memories.

Directed forgetting of memories in cocaine users

The use of cocaine is, after heroin, the second most problematic illicit drug worldwide in terms of negative health consequences (United Nations Office on Drugs & Crime, 2014). The popularity of cocaine in Europe has risen in the last years, and it is estimated that about 1.9 million young adults aged 15 to 34 from all European Union countries used cocaine in 2014 (European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction, 2015). Despite the negative consequences associated with repeated drug abuse, cocaine users continue to use the drug. In the last years the focus on cocaine-related cognitive deficits has increased and a number of studies have examined the long-term effects of cocaine on cognitive processes when comparing users to cocaine-free individuals (Goldstein et al., 2004; Jovanovski, Erb, & Zakzanis, 2005; Woicik et al., 2009). Typically observed impairments include deficits in cognitive flexibility (Verdejo-García & Pérez-García, 2007), episodic memory (Reske, Eidt, Delis, & Paulus, 2010; Vonmoos et al., 2013), inhibitory control processes (Fillmore & Rush, 2002; Volkow et al., 2010), social and non-social decision-making (Hulka et al., 2014), prosodic and cross-modal emotion processing (Hulka et al., 2013), and the control of semantic interference in language production (Ruiz, Paolieri, Colzato, & Bajo, 2015). Thus, many processes that regulate thought and action seem to be impaired after long-term consumption (Block, Erwin, & Ghoneim, 2002; Jovanovski et al., 2005). Chronic users, compared to non-users, show impaired performance on a variety of tasks that measure executive control related-functions: a poorer ability to inhibit overt responses (Fillmore & Rush, 2002), a compromised performance on tasks measuring flexibility (Verdejo-García & Pérez-García, 2007), dysfunctions in attention switching (Kübler, Murphy, & Garavan, 2005), and a poor performance on decision-making tasks (Monterosso, Ehrman, Napier, O'Brien, & Childress, 2001). In particular inhibition, the ability to stop predominant responses or suppress irrelevant information, has been highlighted as a relevant impairment

in stimulant abusers (Fillmore & Rush, 2002; Morein-Zamir, Simon Jones, Bullmore, Robbins, & Ersche, 2015; Morie et al., 2014). The fronto-striatal circuitry is proposed as the neural substrate for inhibitory control (Bari & Robbins, 2013; Miller & Cohen, 2001) and dopamine, the neurotransmitter targeted by cocaine (Hershey et al., 2004) plays an important neuromodulatory role (Arnsten, Wang, & Paspalas, 2012; Robbins & Arnsten, 2009). In this regard, response-inhibition has proven a useful cognitive function to gauge the integrity of fronto-striatal systems in stimulants drugs users (Morein-Zamir & Robbins, 2014).

Recent studies show that an increasing population of recreational cocaine polydrug users, who do not meet the criteria for abuse or dependence but take cocaine on a monthly frequency (1-4 g per month), show similar cognitive impairments to chronic cocaine users. For example, in the study of Colzato, van den Wildenberg, and Hommel (2007), it was shown that recreational cocaine polydrug users experience impairments in response inhibition, but not response execution, measured through a stop-signal task. They also do not show the phenomenon of inhibition of return as compared to non-cocaine users (Colzato & Hommel, 2009). Furthermore, recent studies show that recreational use of cocaine is also associated with impairments on tasks tapping sustained attention and attentional shifting (Soar, Mason, Potton, & Dawkins, 2012; Vonmoos et al., 2013) and the emergence and resolution of response conflict (Sellaro, Hommel, & Colzato, 2013).

Many studies have consistently demonstrated difficulties in the ability to inhibit responses in cocaine users (Colzato et al., 2007; Fillmore & Rush, 2002; Morie et al., 2014). Inhibition represents a family of processes, rather than a single unitary process, that acts at different stages of information processing. For this reason, Miyake and colleagues (2000) proposed two processes that distinguish between the stopping of dominant responses (behavioral inhibition) and the capacity to suppress interference, i.e. the exclusion of non-relevant information in accordance with the demands of the current situation (cognitive

inhibition). This cognitive inhibition permits the selection of relevant information and avoids the irrelevant information that can interfere during processing stage (Harnishfeger, 1995; Nigg, 2000). Similarly, memory retrieval requires suppression of no-longer relevant information from memory and its replacement with new information through an inhibitory-like mechanism (Anderson, 2003; Bjork, 1998).

To date, much research has sought to clarify the relationship between drug abuse and inhibitory control using selective attention and action control tasks (see Bardo et al., 2011), however few studies have studied specifically the plausible impairment of intentional memory suppression in drug abuse (Noël et al., 2009; Zou, Zhang, Huang, & Weng, 2011). For this reason, the present paper explores whether cocaine abuse may contribute to impairments in intentional suppression in episodic memory. In order to examine this possibility, we used a directed forgetting (DF) task using the list method (Bjork, 1970; MacLeod, 1999), in which participants are overtly instructed to forget recently encoded items, inducing memory impairment for those items. In the list version of DF, participants are presented with a list of items to be studied for later recall. After presentation of the first list, participants in the forget condition are instructed to forget the items they have just learned. Following these instructions, a second list is presented, and participants are required to learn these new items. For the recall test, they are asked to remember the items from both lists. As a control, there is a remember condition where participants are presented two lists of items, and they are instructed to remember both. That is, participants in the remember condition also learn two lists but they are not instructed to forget the first one before presentation of the second list. Although the procedure usually involves comparison of two groups, remember and forget, directed forgetting effects are also observed in within-participant designs, where all participants performed the remember task in the first session and the forget task in the second session (e.g., Soriano et al., 2009). Two findings are observed consistently: First, *cost*

effects triggered by the instruction to forget, where people's recall is impaired for List 1 items in the forget condition as compared to List 1 recall in the remember condition (cost 1). Similarly, the recall of List 1 in the forget condition is impaired as compared to List 2 recall in the forget condition (cost 2). Second, when participants forget the first list, they often recall more List 2 items on the final test when compared to the remember condition. This provides a clear *benefit effect* from the instruction to forget that comes from a reduction in proactive interference from the forgotten List 1. These comparisons between lists and instructions to estimate *cost* and *benefit* effects are crucial to show if there is a quantifiable and significant intentional suppression of memories and if cocaine users and their control groups differ in the efficacy of these intentional suppression processes. Therefore, the so-called directed forgetting effects (figure 1) are taken as measures of memory suppression (Bjork, Bjork, & Anderson, 1998; Bjork, 1998; MacLeod, 1999).

Although there are alternative accounts of the DF effects and there might be more than one possible factor underlying them, current theories favor an account in terms of inhibition (Anderson & Hanslmayr, 2014; Bjork, 1998; see Sahakyan & Kelley, 2002 for a contextual-based account). This account assumes that instructions to forget will convert List 1 items to potential competitors that may suffer a transitory state of inhibition, which is regulated by a control mechanism that reduces the accessibility of List 1 items (Anderson & Green, 2001; Bjork et al., 1998). Several studies have found reduced DF effects in populations thought to suffer executive control deficits, such as the elderly (Aguirre, Gómez-Ariza, Bajo, Andrés, & Mazzoni, 2014; Zacks & Hasher, 1994), young children (Harnishfeger & Pope, 1996), frontal-lobe damaged patients (Conway & Fthenaki, 2003), and patients with schizophrenia (Soriano et al., 2009). More relevant for our work is that impaired DF seems to be impaired in abstinent heroin addicts (Zou et al., 2011) and abstinent individuals with alcoholism (Noël et al., 2009) who show greater susceptibility to proactive

interference.

In this paper, we investigated whether cocaine use may impair the mechanism responsible for intentional forgetting of memories in chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation (Experiment 1) and recreational cocaine polydrug users (Experiment 2), by using a DF procedure (Bjork et al., 1998) in which participants were overtly instructed to self-initiate the forgetting of recently acquired information. Based on recent research showing deficits in inhibitory control in cocaine users we expected reduced DF effects for both chronic users (Experiment 1) and recreational users (Experiment 2) relative to matched cocaine-free control participants.

General methods

Apparatus, Stimuli and Procedure

All participants were tested individually. Participants first completed a drug use questionnaire, then they performed the screening and the intelligence task, and finally the DF task using the list method. In this task participants were told that they would be presented with two lists of words to learn that they would have to recall later. The DF procedure's stimuli consisted of two lists of ten words each that were matched on frequency and word length (stimuli were drawn from Soriano & Bajo, 2007). For the *remember* condition and the *forget* condition, two lists of ten words each were randomly taken from a pool of twenty words: ten words served as stimuli for List 1 and the remaining words constituted the List 2 stimuli. The two lists were randomly assigned to the condition of forget or remember instructions. Item order within the lists was randomized for each participant and each list was equally often used in the condition of remember and forget, and equally often served as the first or second presented list. The experiment had a 2 x 2 x 2 mixed design, with instructions (remember or forget) and list output (List 1 and List 2) as within-subjects factors and group

(chronic cocaine users in abstinence or recreational cocaine polydrug users and controls) as the between-subjects factor.

In the *remember* condition, participants were instructed to study two list of items. First, a List 1 was presented in the center of a computer screen in intervals of two seconds. Second, after a pause, List 2 items were also presented for studying. Once List 1 and List 2 were presented, participants were required to count backwards from a three-digit number in steps of three for 30 seconds as a distractor task to control for recency effects. After this, participants were given a sheet of paper and were asked to freely recall as many of the words as they could from both lists.

The *forget* condition was similar to the *remember* condition with the exception of the forget instructions provided after studying List 1. Participants were told that List 1 was just a practice list to familiarize them with the procedure; and they were asked to forget the just presented items and to remember only the next list, which was the *real experimental* list that they would have to recall later. At recall, they were asked to recall all of the words they were presented, even the words they had been told to forget. The experiment was conducted in two sessions. The order of the conditions remained fixed for all participants, since results by Zellner and Bäuml (2006) and Soriano and Bajo (2007) have shown that the order of conditions does not affect the DF effect. Also, presenting the remember condition first avoided confronting the participants with the surprise test after the first session, and having to give them further instructions to ensure that they would not be deceived again (see Soriano et al., 2009 for a similar procedure). To avoid that participants noticed that both tasks were related, care was taken that a period between 1 and 3 months elapsed between the two sessions.

Figure 1

In both experiments, participants were matched for race, age, and IQ [measured by Raven's standard progressive matrices (Raven et al., 1988)]. Furthermore, to ensure intact verbal and memory functions, the participants preformed a Boston naming test (Kaplan, Goodglass, & Weintraub, 1983), a modified version of the verbal fluency test (VFT) for native Spanish speakers from SCIP [Screen for cognitive impairment in psychiatric patients] (Pino et al., 2006), and the memory span test (Daneman & Carpenter, 1980). Participants filled in a self-report questionnaire on recent use, amounts, and patterns of alcohol and drug consumption during the last six months (cf. Colzato et al., 2007). Chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation were screened for other drug use. We found that they only used cocaine except for one participant, who had also used MDMA. Recreational cocaine users, on the other hand, sporadically used other drugs such as MDMA or cannabis, but they mainly and preferably used cocaine. As the recreational users were not "pure" cocaine users, this group of users was called "recreational cocaine polydrug users". To encourage participants' compliance with the instructions, saliva samples were obtained (not further analyzed) at the beginning of the experiment (cf. Colzato, Erasmus & Hommel, 2004). We obtained written informed consent from all participants after providing them with an explanation of the nature of the experiment. The local ethics committee approved the protocol and the compensation of 20 euros for participation in the study.

Statistical Analysis

Analyses were performed using IBM SPSS statistics® 20. In both experiments we adopted a significance level of $p < .05$. Independent samples *t*-tests were used to analyze binary comparisons and analyses of variance (ANOVAs) were used for other group comparisons. We performed *t*-tests for analysis of age, IQ, alcohol consumption, and neuropsychological screening task differences between the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation group or the recreational cocaine users groups, and cocaine-free controls.

Differences between groups in the DF effects were analyzed using repeated measures ANOVA, with group (chronic cocaine users in abstinence or recreational cocaine polydrug users vs. cocaine-free controls) as between-subjects factor. We also performed interquartile analyses for outlier detection. The results of these analyses indicated that two participants from experiment 1 (one in the control group and one chronic cocaine user) were classified as outliers and they were excluded from the analyses. Newman-Keuls *post hoc* analyses were carried out on the critical comparisons to assess DF effects. Partial correlation coefficients were computed between relevant cocaine use variables (e.g., lifetime amount, times per week of cocaine use, maximum peak in 12 hours, and monthly consumed cocaine in grams) and cognitive performance on the DF task in order to test whether the magnitude of cognitive impairments is proportional to the amount of cocaine consumed and to control for the consumption of those drugs (alcohol, tobacco, and cannabis) that varied significantly between the cocaine groups and controls. Effect magnitudes were assessed by calculating partial eta squared (η^2_p).

Experiment 1

Participants

Thirty-eight adults (33 men and 5 women) participated in the experiments. They formed the two experimental groups of 19 chronic users in rehabilitation and 19 cocaine-free controls. **Ten of the participants in Experiment 1 were reengaged from a previous study of the same authors (Ruiz et al., 2015).** Chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation were recruited from *Proyecto Hombre Granada* rehabilitation center. Before their participation in the rehabilitation program, chronic users were taking cocaine on a daily basis for several years ($M=8.92$, $SD=4.67$) administered by snorting route. Cocaine abstinence is a requirement to attend the rehabilitation program, and at the moment of experimental testing, they were

cocaine abstinent for several months ($M=4.71$, $SD=4.03$). The inclusion criteria were: 1) meeting the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM)-IV criteria for cocaine dependence as assessed by the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV disorders (SCID) (American Psychological Association, 2000) – Clinician version (First, Spitzer, Gibbon, & Williams, 1997); 2) a minimum abstinence interval of 30 days for all abuse substances except tobacco, checked by periodic urine toxicology tests, therapists or self-reports. The exclusion criteria were 1) the presence of any Axis I or Axis II disorders except substance abuse, determined by the Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI) (Lecrubier et al., 1997), a brief diagnostic tool that screens for several psychiatric disorders; 2) a history of brain injury or central nervous system diseases; 3) an excessive intake of alcohol (>280 g/week for men and >168g/week for women) (Foster & Marriott, 2006). At the time of the assessment, individuals in the rehabilitation program were free of psychiatric prescription medication. Nineteen adults comprised the control group. We recruited the control participants via notes posted on community bulletin boards and by word of mouth. Control group individuals did not meet any Axis I or Axis II psychiatric disorders, including substance abuse (except for tobacco) and no clinically significant medical disease (e.g. multiple sclerosis). Participants in the two groups were matched on race, age, and IQ [measured by Raven's standard progressive matrices (Raven et al., 1988)].

In the last six months, prior to participation, five chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation and three cocaine-free users also smoked marijuana, while one chronic cocaine user in rehabilitation reported having used MDMA (ecstasy). All participants reported never using ketamine, LSD, steroids, GHB, barbiturates or opioids. Although chronic cocaine users in the rehabilitation group were engaged in the detoxification program, they were periodically (every 30 days) screened for drug use through urine analysis, and we asked them to refrain from taking all types of psychoactive drugs for at least two days before the experiment. In

addition, all participants were asked not to consume alcohol the night before the experimental session and to have a normal night of rest.

Table 1

Results

Demographics and drug use statistics are provided in Table 1. As mentioned, we assessed the alcohol habits of the participants through a self-reported questionnaire enquiring about their weekly intake of alcoholic drinks. Since the strengths of different types of alcoholic beverages vary significantly, we adopted the definitions of standard "drinks" or "units," equal to a 10 ml or 8 grams of pure ethanol (International Center for Alcohol Policies, 2005). As can be observed in Table 1, chronic cocaine users differed from controls in the amount of tobacco, alcohol, and cannabis consumed before they entered into the rehabilitation program, although all of them were not consuming alcohol or cannabis once they entered into the program.

Table 2

To ensure intact verbal and memory functions, the participants performed several screening tasks: a Boston naming test (Kaplan et al., 1983), a modified version of test of verbal fluency (VFT) for native Spanish speakers from SCIP [Screen for cognitive impairment in psychiatric patients] (Pino et al., 2006) and the memory span test (Daneman & Carpenter, 1980). No significant group differences were obtained for intelligence, $t(36) = -1.49, p=.14$; memory span test, $t(36) = -1.63, p=.11$; Boston naming task, $t(36) = -1.31, p=.19$ or verbal fluency, $t(36) = 0.82, p=.41$. Table 2 shows performance on the intelligence and neuropsychological tests.

Figure 2

Figure 2 shows the mean number of words recalled for each condition of the DF experiment. The results of the ANOVA on correct recall with group (chronic cocaine users and cocaine-free controls) as a between-subjects factor and instructions (forget and remember) and List (List 1 and List 2) as within-subjects factors showed a significant main effect of group [$F(1, 36) = 32.63, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .47$]. This indicated that the cocaine-free control group remembered more items ($M=4.66, SD=1.93$) relative to the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation group ($M = 2.75, SD = 1.34$). Moreover, the main effect of List was significant [$F(1, 36) = 21.35, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .37$] showing that more items were recalled for List 2 ($M=4.16, SD=2.03$) than for List 1 ($M=3.25, SD=1.67$). The interaction List x group was significant [$F(1, 36) = 11.64, p = .002, \eta^2_p = .24$]. *Post hoc* Newman-Keuls analyses showed that the control group remembered fewer List 1 items ($M=3.87, SD=1.76$) relative to List 2 items ($M=5.45, SD=1.78$) [$p < .001$], whereas this difference between List 1 ($M=2.63, SD=1.34$) and List 2 ($M=2.87, SD=1.34$) was not present for the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation ($p = .39$). Importantly, the interaction List x instructions was significant [$F(1, 36) = 21.35, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .37$]. *Post hoc* Newman-Keuls analyses showed the typical DF effect with less List 1 items recalled in the forgetting condition ($M=2.71, SD=1.56$) than List 2 items in the remember condition ($M=4.55, SD=2.13$) [$p < .01$]. The three-way interaction instructions x List x group was significant [$F(1, 36) = 4.61, p = .039, \eta^2_p = .11$]¹. To further analyze this interaction, we performed *post hoc* Newman-Keuls procedure for the cocaine-free controls and chronic cocaine users groups to explore *cost* and *benefit effects*.

First, we analyzed the *costs* of instructions to forget on List 1. These comparisons indicated, first, that cocaine-free controls' recall for the List 1 items of the forget condition

¹ To verify whether the high alcohol use in chronic cocaine users may have confounded this outcome, we ran another ANOVA with alcohol intake as a covariate; however, the crucial three-way interaction remained significant: $F(1, 35) = 4.48, p = .041, \eta^2_p = .11$.

($M=3.16$, $SD=1.8$) was significantly lower than the recall of List 1 items in the remember condition ($M=4.58$, $SD=1.43$) [$p = .001$], whereas chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation did not forget significantly more List 1 items in the forget task ($M=2.26$, $SD=1.15$) than in the remember task ($M=3$, $SD=1.45$) [$p = .27$] (see figure 2). Similarly, comparison of recall from List 1 items in the forget condition relative to List 2 items in the forget condition was significant for the control group [$p < .001$], whereas the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation did not show this difference [$p = .17$].

Lastly, we analyzed the *benefits* of forgetting. This comparison showed that cocaine-free controls recalled more List 2 items in the forget condition ($M=6.11$, $SD=1.63$) than in the remember condition ($M=4.79$, $SD=1.72$) [$p < .002$]. However, for the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation the recall of List 2 items in the forget condition ($M=3$, $SD=1.25$) as compared to the remember condition ($M=2.74$, $SD=1.45$) was not significantly different [$p = .52$].

Finally, to avoid that the directed forgetting effects may be masked by the low overall baseline performance in the chronic cocaine group, we performed an overall ANOVA as previously described on the data from participants in both groups showing similar levels of recall in both groups (10 controls and 10 chronic cocaine users). We did not find a significant effect of group [$p = .12$]. A significant List effect [$F(1, 18) = 12.6$, $p = .002$, $\eta^2_p = .41$] showed that items belonging to List 2 are better recalled ($M=4.05$, $SD=1.67$) than items belonging to List 1 ($M=2.97$, $SD=1.57$). A significant interaction between List and group [$F(1, 18) = 4.97$, $p = .039$, $\eta^2_p = .21$] showed that the cocaine-free control group recalled more List 2 items ($M=4.7$, $SD=1.75$) compared to the chronic cocaine users ($M=3.4$, $SD=1.35$). The effect of instructions was marginally significant [$F(1, 18) = 4.18$, $p = .055$, $\eta^2_p = .18$], reflecting that more words were recalled under the instructions to remember ($M=3.82$, $SD=1.33$) than under the instructions to forget ($M=3.2$, $SD=1.67$). The interaction List x instruction was also significant [$F(1, 18) = 15.36$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .46$], showing that items belonging to List 1 are

suppressed in the forget condition ($M=2.15$, $SD=1.3$) compared to List 2 items ($M=4.25$, $SD=2$). The three-way interaction instructions x List x group reached significance [$F(1, 18) = 9.95$, $p = .005$, $\eta^2_p = .35$]. We analyzed the *costs* of instructions to forget on List 1. These comparisons indicated that cocaine-free controls' recall for the List 1 items of the forget condition ($M=4$, $SD=1.24$) was significantly lower than the recall of List 1 items in the remember condition ($M=1.9$, $SD=1.28$) [$p = .01$], whereas chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation did not forget significantly more List 1 items in the forget task ($M=2.4$, $SD=1.34$) than in the remember task ($M=3.6$, $SD=1.57$) [$p = .082$]. Similarly, comparisons of recall from List 1 items in the forget condition relative to List 2 items in the forget condition was significant for the control group [$p < .001$], whereas the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation did not show this difference [$p = .26$]. Finally, we analyzed the *benefits* of forgetting. This comparison showed that cocaine-free controls recalled more List 2 items in the forget condition ($M=5.5$, $SD=1.64$) than in the remember condition ($M=3.9$, $SD=1.52$) [$p = .02$]. However, for the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation the recall of List 2 items in the forget condition ($M=3$, $SD=1.5$) as compared to the remember condition ($M=3.8$, $SD=1.13$) was not significantly different [$p = .30$].

Finally, no significant partial correlations coefficients were found between relevant cocaine use variables (individual lifetime cocaine exposure, maximum peak in 12 h and weekly consumption in grams) and the DF effect, when controlling for the use of alcohol, MDMA and tobacco.

Discussion

Experiment 1 aimed to test the hypothesis that chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation may have some difficulties when attempting to intentionally forget no-longer relevant information when instructed to do so, even when instructions stressed that this information

might interfere with recall of relevant information. Results show that while cocaine-free controls show the typical memory suppression effects associated with the directed forgetting procedure, the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation showed smaller non-significant effects. That is, the usual impairment of List 1 items relative List 2 when instructed to forget or the diminished recall of List 1 items in the forget condition relative to List 1 in the remember condition were reduced in the chronic cocaine users and differed from the larger cost effects showed by the control-cocaine free group. In addition, chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation did not show reliable *benefits* of List 1 forgetting. Thus, recall of List 2 in forget and recall conditions was similar for the users, whereas the cocaine-free controls showed better recall of List 2 in the forget than in the remember condition. Presumably, chronic cocaine users had more difficulties in suppressing information from List 1 as instructed, and they were not able to benefit from it, possibly because List 1 forgetting might not have been strong enough to produce this benefit so that chronic users still suffer from proactive interference.

In order to assess whether other cocaine users who do not qualify as *chronic* cocaine users but often consume cocaine for recreational purposes, would more clearly show intentional forgetting deficits, we conducted a new experiment with the same materials and procedure as Experiment 1, but testing recreational cocaine polydrug users' ability to forget non-relevant memories.

Experiment 2

Participants

Forty-four healthy adults (21 men and 23 women) served as participants for partial fulfillment of course credits or a financial compensation. These constituted both the recreational cocaine polydrug users and cocaine-free controls. We recruited the participants via notes posted on community bulletin boards and by word of mouth. **Six of the participants**

in experiments 2 were reengaged from a previous study of the same authors (Ruiz et al., 2015). Recreational cocaine polydrug users met the following criteria: 1) a monthly consumption (1 to 4 grams) by snorting for a minimum of two years; 2) no axis I or Axis II psychiatric disorders [DSM-IV (American Psychological Association, 2000)], including substance abuse other than cocaine and tobacco; 3) no clinically significant medical disease; 4) no use of prescription medication. Cocaine-free controls met the same criteria except they reported no history of past or current cocaine use. Participants were selected by means of a phone interview using the MINI (Lecrubier et al., 1997), a brief diagnostic tool that screens for several psychiatric disorders. The sample was obtained from a pool of approximately 50 potential volunteers who responded to the advertisements for studies conducted in our lab over a period of six months. Within this pool of potential participants, the most common reason for excluding an individual from the study was meeting criteria for psychiatric disorders (psychotic symptoms, anxiety and depression), alcohol abuse or medication. Furthermore, to ensure intact verbal and memory functioning the participants performed a Boston naming test (Kaplan et al., 1983), a modified version of VFT for native Spanish speakers from SCIP (Pino et al., 2006), and the memory span test (Daneman & Carpenter, 1980).

Participants were asked to refrain from taking all psychoactive drugs for at least two days, not to consume alcohol on the night before the experimental session, and to have a normal night rest. To encourage participants' compliance with the instructions, saliva samples were obtained (not further analyzed) at the beginning of the experiment (cf. Colzato, Erasmus & Hommel 2004).

In the six months prior to participation, thirteen recreational cocaine polydrug users smoked cannabis while seventeen recreational users reported having used MDMA (ecstasy) and eleven reported using ketamine. Participants in the two groups were matched on race, age

and IQ (Raven et al., 1988). All participants reported never using LSD, steroids, GHB, barbiturates or opioids.

Figure 3

Results

Demographics and drug use statistics are provided in Table 1. No significant group differences were obtained for intelligence, $t(42) = 0.18, p = .85$; memory span test, $t(42) = 1.40, p = .47$; Boston naming task, $t(42) = -0.36, p = .71$; or verbal fluency, $t(42) = -0.72, p = .47$. Table 2 shows performance on the intelligence and neuropsychological tests. We performed an overall ANOVA with group (recreational cocaine polydrug users and controls) as between-subjects factor and instructions (forget and remember) and List (List 1 and List 2) as within-subjects factors (see Figure 3). A significant main effect of group [$F(1, 42) = 6.44, p = .02, \eta^2_p = .13$] indicated that the control group remembered more items ($M = 5.17, SD = 2.64$) than the group of recreational cocaine polydrug users ($M = 3.93, SD = 1.94$). The main effect of List was significant [$F(1, 42) = 5.74, p = .02, \eta^2_p = .12$] showing that List 2 recall was better ($M = 4.88, SD = 2.42$) than List 1 recall ($M = 4.21, SD = 2.31$). The main effect of instructions was not significant ($F < 1$), but the interaction between List x group reached significance [$F(1, 42) = 4.29, p = .04, \eta^2_p = .09$]. *Post hoc* Newman-Keuls analyses showed that the control group remembered fewer List 1 items ($M = 4.54, SD = 2.52$) relative to List 2 items ($M = 5.79, SD = 2.62$) [$p = .003$], whereas this difference between List 1 ($M = 3.88, SD = 2.00$) and List 2 ($M = 3.97, SD = 1.87$) was not present for the recreational cocaine polydrug users ($p = .82$). The interaction between List and instructions was significant [$F(1, 42) = 27.42, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .39$]. *Post hoc* Newman-Keuls analyses showed the typical DF effect with fewer List 1 items being recalled in the forgetting condition ($M = 3.65, SD = 2.29$) than in the remember condition ($M = 4.77, SD = 2.17$) [$p < .003$]. The interaction between instructions, List and group

was significant [$F(1, 42) = 13.02, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .23$]². To further analyze this interaction, we performed additional *post hoc* Newman-Keuls analyses for the cocaine-free controls and recreational cocaine polydrug users groups to explore *cost* and *benefit effects*.

First, we analyzed the *costs* of the instruction to forget List 1. These comparisons indicated, first, that cocaine-free controls' recall for the List 1 items of the forget condition ($M=3.68, SD=2.47$) was significantly less than the recall of List 1 items on the remember task ($M=5.40, SD=2.32$) [$p = .005$], whereas recreational cocaine polydrug users did not forget significantly more List 1 items on the forget task ($M=3.63, SD=2.15$) than in the remember task ($M=4.13, SD=1.85$) [$p = .80$]. Similarly, comparison of recall from List 1 items in the forget condition relative to List 2 items in the forget condition was significant for the control group [$p < .001$], whereas the recreational cocaine polydrug users did not show this difference [$p = .74$]. Finally, we analyzed the *benefits* of forgetting. This comparison showed that cocaine-free controls recalled more List 2 items in the forget condition ($M=6.9, SD=2.22$) than in the remember condition ($M=4.68, SD=2.57$) [$p < .001$]. However, for the recreational cocaine polydrug users the recall of List 2 items in the forget condition ($M=4.1, SD=1.94$) compared to the remember condition ($M=3.86, SD=1.83$) was not different [$p = .61$]. The results of the direct comparison of the benefit index in the two groups (subtracting recall of List 2 in the forget condition from recall of List 2 in the remember condition) also yielded significant group differences for the effect of *benefit*, $t(42) = 2.69, p = .01$, indicating that cocaine-free controls achieved higher benefits from inhibiting List 1 item under the forget condition. **Due to the similar number of males and females in the sample of experiment 2, we performed a secondary analysis with sex (males and females) as a between subject factor, and**

² To verify whether the high alcohol use in recreational cocaine users may have confounded this outcome, we ran another ANOVA with alcohol intake as a covariate; however, the crucial 3-way interaction remained significant: $F(1, 41) = 9.61, p = .003, \eta^2_p = .19$.

instructions (forget and remember) and List (List 1 and List 2) as a within-subject factor. The results of the main effect of List and the List x instruction interaction remained significant [$p < .05$], however, the main effect of sex, the interactions of List x sex, the interaction of instructions x sex, and the three-way interaction instructions x List x sex were not significant [$p > .05$]. Hence, sex seems not to modulate the obtained effects

Finally, to avoid that the directed forgetting effect may be masked by the low overall baseline performance in the recreational cocaine polydrug group, we compared and analyzed the data from the participants in the two groups showing similar level of recall in both groups. Thus, individuals from both groups (19 controls and 19 chronic cocaine users) with similar recall performance were compared using an ANOVA as previously described. We did not find a significant effect of group [$p = .17$]. A significant List effect [$F(1, 36) = 4.95, p = .03, \eta^2_p = .12$] showed that items belonging to List 2 were better recalled ($M = 4.65, SD = 2.23$) than items belonging to List 1 ($M = 3.98, SD = 2$). A significant interaction between List and group [$F(1, 36) = 4.57, p = .04, \eta^2_p = .11$] showed that the cocaine-free control group recalled more List 2 items ($M = 5.28, SD = 2.4$) compared to the recreational polydrug users ($M = 4, SD = 1.88$). The main effect of instructions did not reach significance [$F < 1$]. The interaction List x instruction was also significant [$F(1, 36) = 30.46, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .46$], showing that items belonging to List 1 are more suppressed in the forget condition ($M = 3.42, SD = 2.17$) compared to List 2 items ($M = 5.31, SD = 2.38$). The three-way interaction instructions x List x group reached significance [$F(1, 36) = 13.98, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .28$].

We analyzed the *costs* of instructions to forget on List 1. These comparisons indicated that cocaine-free controls' recall for the List 1 items of the forget condition ($M = 3.17, SD = 2.21$) was significantly lower than the recall of List 1 items in the remember condition ($M = 4.78, SD = 1.81$) [$p = .01$], whereas chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation did not forget significantly more List 1 items in the forget task ($M = 3.68, SD = 2.16$) than in the remember

task ($M=4.31$, $SD=1.73$) [$p = .61$]. Similarly, comparison of recall from List 1 items in the forget condition relative to List 2 items in the forget condition was significant for the control group [$p < .001$], whereas the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation did not show this difference [$p = .77$]. Finally, we analyzed the *benefits* of forgetting. This comparison showed that cocaine-free controls recalled more List 2 items in the forget condition ($M=6.52$, $SD=2.11$) than in the remember condition ($M=3.94$, $SD=1.77$) [$p < .001$]. However, for the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation the recall of List 2 items in the forget condition ($M=4.10$, $SD=2$) as compared to the remember condition ($M=3.94$, $SD=1.77$) was not significantly different [$p = .93$].

Finally, no significant partial correlations coefficients were found between relevant cocaine use variables (individual lifetime cocaine exposure, maximum peak in 12 h and weekly consumption in grams) and the DF effect, when controlling for the use of alcohol, MDMA and tobacco.

Discussion

Experiment 2 aimed to investigate whether recreational cocaine polydrug users showed impaired intentional inhibitory processes during episodic memory retrieval. Results clearly indicate that recreational cocaine polydrug users showed a reduction in the usual memory suppression effect associated with the directed forgetting procedure. Thus, the usual impairment of List 1 items relative to List 2 when instructed to forget List 1 items in the forget condition relative to List 1 in the remember condition was smaller than that observed in the control group and did not reach significance. Similarly, they did not show the *benefit* of forgetting, i.e., recall of List 2 items in the forget condition was similar to the recall of List 2 items in the remember condition. As the DF effect is usually interpreted as the result of intentional forgetting mechanisms (Anderson & Hanslmayr, 2014), this pattern of results

suggests that recreational cocaine polydrug users are impaired in their ability to intentionally suppress List 1 items to prevent interference from List 2 items. The results show that although recreational cocaine polydrug users do not use the drug on a daily basis, their monthly continuous small amounts of cocaine ($M=3.80$, $SD=3.90$) seem to impact inhibitory processes engaged in the suppression of irrelevant information in episodic memory.

General Discussion

This study investigated for the first time the dynamics of intentional forgetting in chronic users in rehabilitation and recreational polydrug users of cocaine, who were carefully screened and matched to cocaine-free control participants performing a directed forgetting task. Different methods have been used to elicit the DF effect (see Basden & Basden, 1998; MacLeod, 1999). In the present research we used the list method to elicit the inhibitory processes engaged during remembering. Several lines of research have proposed inhibition as the mechanism underlying this effect (Anderson & Hanslmayr, 2014; but see Sahakyan & Kelley, 2002, for a non-inhibitory account). In addition, there is evidence supporting the impairment of inhibitory processes in chronic and recreational cocaine users (Colzato et al., 2007; Ersche et al., 2012; Fillmore & Rush, 2002; Volkow et al., 2010). Given the recruitment of inhibitory mechanisms in intentional forgetting and the impairment of these mechanisms due to cocaine use, it creates a perfect scenario to test the relationship between them by comparing the performance of chronic users in rehabilitation, recreational cocaine polydrug users, and a cocaine-free control group on their ability to actively inhibit irrelevant information in their episodic memory.

The control group in both Experiment 1 and 2 replicated the typical directed forgetting effect observed in seminal studies (Bjork et al., 1998), showing a decrease in the recall of List 1 items under the *forget* instructions with and the typical *cost* and *benefit effects*.

In Experiment 1, we found that chronic cocaine users attending a rehabilitation program did not show a reliable directed forgetting effect. In fact their pattern of recall showed reduced cost and benefit effects relative to the cocaine-free control group, indicating that their ability to intentionally suppress irrelevant information from memory was less efficient than that shown by the control group. Similarly, in Experiment 2 recreational cocaine polydrug users also showed impairment in their ability to intentionally suppress information and they did not show reliable directed forgetting effects. These results suggest that cocaine consumption is related to a deficit in intentional forgetting. In addition, the results of the reduced directed forgetting effect in recreational cocaine polydrug users, compared to the control group, allow us to speculate that even the use of small amounts of cocaine results in poorer performance in effectively triggering the inhibitory mechanism.

The results in the present paper are in line with those studies that suggest that even small amounts of cocaine used regularly are connected to deficits in executive control processes (Colzato et al., 2007). In addition, the results of impaired performance of inhibitory mechanism in episodic memory in chronic and recreational cocaine polydrug users are in agreement with the results reported by Ruiz et al., (2015) showing a deficit in the ability to inhibit interfering information in language production in both chronic and recreational cocaine users. The apparent link between cocaine abuse and this deficit in memory suppression highlights the variety of inhibitory processes that may be altered by the abuse of stimulant drugs that act on the catecholaminergic synapses in brain areas that regulate and control executive processes. Our results cannot be explained by several potentially confounding factors, since our participants were screened for several psychiatric disorders (schizophrenia, ADHD or obsessive-compulsive disorder) that have been associated with dopaminergic alterations (Davis, Kahn, Ko, & Davidson, 1991; Pooley, Fineberg, & Harrison, 2007; Tripp & Wickens, 2008). Similarly, the deficits in inhibitory effects are not

due to the use of other drugs such as MDMA or cannabis, since they were screened for the use of these substances. In addition, given that MDMA has been associated with impairments in working memory processes, cannabis leads to dysfunction in cognitive flexibility (Verdejo-García, López-Torrecillas, Aguilar de Arcos, & Pérez-García, 2005), and both drugs seem unrelated to the production of impairments in inhibitory control, we doubt that our results can be attributed to the consumption of cannabis or MDMA. Moreover, since our groups were matched on age, this factor cannot explain our results even though the directed forgetting phenomenon appears to diminish in populations thought to suffer deficits in executive control, such as in the elderly (Aguirre et al., 2014; Zacks & Hasher, 1994) or due to the decline of inhibitory efficiency associated with aging (Williams, Ponesse, Schachar, Logan, & Tannock, 1999). In addition, although we screened participants for alcohol consumption in both experiments, since previous research relates acute and long-term use of alcohol to impairments on inhibitory control (Fillmore & Vogel-Sprott, 2000; Noël et al., 2009). However, despite these efforts to control the alcohol consumption in both experiments, the alcohol use history of chronic and recreational users of cocaine may still be exerting an influence on the putative cocaine use-related findings. Notwithstanding, given that impaired inhibitory control could promote excessive drinking, it is reasonable that individuals who experience a greater malfunction of inhibitory control should be likely to drink alcoholic drinks more excessively (Weafer & Fillmore, 2008).

It is interesting to note that both chronic users in rehabilitation and recreational cocaine users showed an overall memory deficit, and this deficit does not seem to recover after a short period of abstinence since it is still present in the chronic in rehabilitation group. This is consistent with prior research with both recreational users and abstinent chronic users in rehabilitation that shows persistent impairments in verbal learning efficiency, which results in deficits in memory storage and recall (Ardila, Rosselli, & Strumwasser, 1991; Beatty,

Katzung, Moreland, & Nixon, 1995; Rosselli & Ardila, 1996). Some studies reported improvement of cognitive processes in cocaine users after cessation of the drug consumption (De Oliveira et al., 2009; Vonmoos et al., 2014; but see Bauer, 1996; van Gorp et al., 1999 for persistent neuropsychological impairment). These studies showed that while cocaine clearly has a significant effect on cognitive functions, cocaine users can eventually return to a normal brain functioning and avoid any permanent damage to their cognitive abilities. Because chronic cocaine use produces neuroadaptations in dopamine systems (Letchworth, Nader, Smith, Friedman, & Porrino, 2001), the reversibility of cognitive deficits after sustained abstinence suggests that neuroplastic adaptations might occur if the repeated pharmacological stimulus is discontinued. However, the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation in Experiment 1 did not show a recovery of cognitive functions after cocaine cessation suggesting that neuroadaptation may be a slow process that needs time to show its effect.

Finally, this study has certain methodological limitations that are common to many neuropsychological studies in the area of substance abuse. First, we did not collect urine samples and this has prevented us to clarify the issue of the relationship between the extent of the cognitive inhibition impairment and the chronic and recreational cocaine use active use of cocaine (cf. Moeller et al., 2016). Second, particularly important was the screening of alcohol consumption in both groups to ensure that participants selected for the study reported an average long-term consumption below the criteria for high alcohol use (280 g/week for men and 168g/week for women). In addition, although participants in Experiment 1 were undergoing regular urine toxicology screens as part of the treatment, some participants in Experiment 2 may have actively used either alcohol or cocaine within 24 to 48 hours prior to the experimental session, potentially affecting the performance in the directed forgetting task. Although tentative, the fact that the impairment appeared in both recreational and chronic

users (urine tested) suggests that this might not have been the case. However, despite the efforts to control the alcohol consumption in both experiments, the alcohol use history of chronic and recreational users of cocaine may be exerting an influence on the putative cocaine use-related findings. Third, the design of our study allows us to reject alternative accounts of our observations in terms of age, IQ, and sex since the two users groups were matched with the controls in these variables. Similarly, the present results cannot be explained by factors regarding pre-existing psychiatric disorders that are known to affect response inhibition (Rosenberg, Dick, O'Hearn, & Sweeney, 1997; Schachar & Logan, 1990) since we performed a wide screening using the MINI to exclude preexisting psychiatric disorders (e.g. ADHD). Nevertheless, the results of this study for both groups do not allow us to completely rule out an account of their deficit in terms of preexistent underlying personality traits of impulsivity and neurocognitive endophenotypes for stimulant drug addiction that may contribute to task performance (Robbins, Gillan, Smith, de Wit, & Ersche, 2012; Smith, Jones, Bullmore, Robbins, & Ersche, 2013). Furthermore, although we interpret the unreliable DF effects for both groups as a deficit in memory suppression due to cocaine consumption, this conclusion must be interpreted with care due to the cross-sectional design of this study and should be replicated through longitudinal studies focusing on this issue.

Another possible shortcoming of our study is that given the abuse rate of other drugs when consuming cocaine among recreational users (Groves, Kelly, & Parsons, 2009), it is difficult to separate the cognitive deficit produced by cocaine use from the effect of the use of other drugs. We tried to minimize this fact by selecting a predominant cocaine users' sample and avoiding as much as possible selecting people that also abuse other stimulant drugs. We based our selection on self-report measures since previous studies have shown that self-reports of drug abuse are quite reliable and strongly correlated with objective measures of drug abuse (Glintborg, Olsen, Poulsen, Linnet, & Dalhoff, 2008; Zaldívar Basurto et al.,

2009). Moreover, although we found highly significant group differences in cigarette smoking in Experiment 1 and 2, the role of tobacco use in a possible neuro-cognitive impairment is not clear (Wagner et al., 2013). In addition, since our participants reported very low consumption of cannabis and MDMA, we doubt that our results may be attributed to the use of any of these two drugs. Moreover, studies that have examined the effect of MDMA and cannabis on executive functions have provided conflicting results. Whereas deficits in working memory appear to be likely consequences of chronic MDMA and impairments in cognitive flexibility due to cannabis use (Verdejo-García et al., 2005), less consistent results were found in studies investigating inhibitory control in the abuse of both substances (Crean, Crane, & Mason, 2011; Kalechstein, De la Garza, Mahoney, Fantegrossi, & Newton, 2007).

Despite these limitations and suggestions for further research, our study clearly suggests that impairments in memory suppression may be associated with cocaine consumption. Cocaine use seems to be associated with a low performance in inhibiting the ability to suppress irrelevant information. In summary, the results found in chronic users in rehabilitation and recreational cocaine users are worrying given that a dysfunctional adaptive mechanism of forgetting may be responsible for a variety of memory distortions in terms of updating information, which affects learning and recall in everyday behavior. This reduced level of memory suppression may even be involved in the emergence of addiction. When drug-related representations breaks through into awareness and are experienced as a craving episode for cocaine, addicted individuals would also find it difficult to suppress them and to resist using cocaine because of an impairment in the suppression of dominant thoughts. Specifically, our findings of dysregulated behavior in ignoring information in declarative memory may perhaps hamper the achievement of a complete rehabilitation (Robbins et al., 2008). The difficulty in suppressing repetitive thoughts of using cocaine might represent the core of a vulnerability to relapse and a weak maintenance of detoxification.

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Figure Legends

Figure 1. The list-method directed forgetting, along with the typical pattern of findings: impaired recall of List 1 and improved recall of List 2 items.

Figure 2. Mean number of recalled words as a function of group, instructions, and List in Experiment 1. Error bars represent standards error of mean. Horizontal lines represent critical comparisons between Lists (1 and 2) and instructions (forget and remember) for the effects of cost (1 and 2) and benefit.

* $p < .05$

^{ns} Non-significant difference.

Figure 3. Mean number of recalled words as a function of group, instructions, and List in Experiment 2. Error bars represent standard error of mean. Horizontal lines represent critical comparisons between Lists (1 and 2) and instructions (forget and remember) for the effects of cost and benefit.

* $p < .05$

^{ns} Non-significant difference.

Remember condition

- List of unrelated words (List 1)
- Remember instructions
- List of unrelated words (List 2)
- Distracting task
- Free recall of List 1 and List 2

Now a second list will appear. You have to study it

Forgetting condition

- List of unrelated words (List 1)
- Forgetting instructions
- List of unrelated words (List 2)
- Distracting task
- Free recall of List 1 and List 2

List 1 was only for practice. You don't need to remember it. You can forget it. Now you have to learn List 2

Table 1

Demographical characteristics and self-reported use of cocaine and other psychoactive drugs in Experiment 1 and 2.

Sample	Experiment 1		Experiment 2	
	Chronic cocaine users	Cocaine-free controls	Recreational cocaine polydrug users	Cocaine-free controls
N (M:F) ^{ns}	19 (16:3)	19 (17:2)	22 (10:12)	22 (11:11)
Age (years) ^{ns}	31.9 (4.7)	29.6 (5.9)	25.1 (3.3)	23.7 (2.7)
Raven IQ ^{ns}	104.7 (7.7)	101.6 (5)	102.7 (7.0)	103.2 (8.8)
Cigarettes (unit/day)	12.6 (7.1)**	1.9 (3.7)	9 (7.3)**	1 (2)
Alcohol (units ¹ /weeks)	26.9 (22.81)**	4.2 (4.9)	15.2 (10.0)**	4.7 (3.7)
Monthly cannabis (joints)	3.6 (7.3) ^{ns}	0.6 (1.5)	8.5 (8.6)**	0
Years using cocaine	8.9 (4.68)	0	4.4 (2.7)	0
Monthly exposure (grams of cocaine)	14.9 (15.9)	0	3.8 (3.9)	0
Maximum amount in a 12-h period (grams)	2.7 (1.6)	0	1.1 (0.6)	0
Mean weeks in abstinence	33 (28.2)	0	2.25 (2.61)	0
Monthly spent money (EUR)	896.8 (956.9)	0	94.5 (61.2)	0
MDMA (grams/ last 6 months)	0.3 (1.5)	0	1.75 (2.0)	0

Note. Raven IQ: IQ measured by means of the Raven's standard progressive matrices.

¹ Unit equals to a 10 ml or 8 grams of pure ethanol (International Center for Alcohol Policies, 2005; Álvarez et al., 2008). Chronic cocaine users are alcohol abstinent once they are engaged in the rehabilitation program.

^{ns} Non-significant difference.

* Significant group difference; $p < .05$

** Significant group difference; $p < .01$

Table 2

Mean scores of neuropsychological test performance in Experiment 1 and 2.

Test	Experiment 1		Experiment 2	
	Chronic cocaine users	Cocaine-free controls	Recreational cocaine polydrug users	Cocaine-free controls
BNT ^{ns}	51.8 (4.9)	49.6 (5.4)	51.9 (4.8)	49.6 (5.2)
VFT ^{ns}	44.4 (8.3)	47 (10.8)	44.5 (8.1)	46.5 (10.7)
MST ^{ns}	3.2 (0.7)	2.78 (1.03)	3.3 (1)	2.8 (1)

Notes. BNT: Boston naming test; VF: verbal fluency test; MST: memory span test.

^{ns} Non-significant difference.

Public Significance Statement

This study suggests that the abuse of cocaine, whether chronic or recreational, leads to an impairment in the cognitive mechanism that allows the suppression of irrelevant memories. It may be translated into a variety of memory distortions in terms of updating information, which affects recall in everyday behavior, causing an erroneous perception of the acquirement of learning or affecting the ability to forget negative autobiographical memories.

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Contributions

All authors contributed in a significant way to the manuscript and have read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of interests

All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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